

Syntheses of Furano Compounds, Part XXXIX

Synthesis of 2-Arylcoumaran-3-ones and 3-Arylcoumaran-2-ones

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A general method involving Curtius reaction for the synthesis of 2-arylcoumaran-3-ones and 3-arylcoumaran-2-ones is described.

CURTIOUS reaction has been successfully applied in the syntheses of oxygen heterocycles^{1,2,3}. In connection with an investigation we required 2- and 3-arylcoumaran-3- or 2-ones which we prepared by the application of Curtius reaction. Thus 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (I) has been converted into the urethane (III) by refluxing the azide (II) with dry methanol. The urethane on boiling with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid and glacial acetic acid gave 2-phenylcoumaran-3-one (VII).

I, R = H, R₁ = COOH

II, R = H, R₁ = CON₃

III, R = H, R₁ = NHCOOCH₃

IV, R = CH₃, R₁ = COOH

V, R = CH₃, R₁ = NHCOOCH₃

VII, R = H

VIII, R = CH₃

VI, R = COOH

IX, R = Ph

Decomposition of the urethane by refluxing with a mixture of hydriodic acid and acetic acid however yielded a mixture of 2-phenylcoumaran-3-one (VII) and 2-phenylcoumarone. The ketone (VII) showed absorption at 1720 cm⁻¹ and in the PMR spectrum showed the 2-H resonance in the aromatic region only. This is due to the fact that the proton is strongly deshielded by the phenyl and the carbonyl group.

Following the same method 2-*p*-tolylcoumaran-3-one (VIII) and 3-phenylcoumaran-2-one (IX) have

been synthesised from 2-*p*-tolylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (IV) and 3-phenylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (VI). The urethane (V) showed i.r. absorption at 3278 cm⁻¹ (NH) and 1700 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl) while the ketone (VIII) showed absorption at 1719 cm⁻¹ for its carbonyl group. 3-Phenylisocoumaran-2-one (IX) showed a broad lactone band around 1800 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237.

2-Phenyl-3-carbomethoxyaminocoumarone: 2-Phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (2 g) suspended in dry benzene (10 ml) was treated with thionyl chloride (1.2 ml) and a drop of pyridine and refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and last traces were removed by two successive addition of dry benzene followed by its removal under reduced pressure. The residual acid chloride was dissolved in dry acetone (20 ml) at 0° and treated with a solution of sodium azide (0.84 g) in water (4.2 ml) dropwise with shaking. After 20 min, cold water (30 ml) was added when the crude azide (1.5 g) separated as light brown solid, m.p. 65° (decomp.). It was collected and dried in vacuum desiccator.

The azido (1.5 g) was refluxed with dry methanol (20 ml) for 2 hr when the solid dissolved after brisk evolution of nitrogen. The solution was concentrated and cooled when crude 2-phenyl-3-carbomethoxyaminocoumarone (1.3 g) was obtained. On crystallisation from methanol it was obtained as cream coloured needles, m.p. 162° (Found: C, 71.9; H, 5.1. C₁₆H₁₃O₃N requires C, 71.9; H, 4.9%).

2-Phenylcoumaran-3-one: *Method A*: 2-Phenyl-3-carbomethoxyaminocoumarone (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 ml) for 28 hr. Acetic acid and hydrochloric acids were removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residual solid was treated with water, filtered and crystallised from acetic acid

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to give colourless cubes of 2-phenylcoumaran-3-one (0.1 g), m.p. 220° (Found : C, 80.0; H, 4.6. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 4.8%); ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

Method B: The above urethane (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed with 48% hydriodic acid (5 ml) for 4 hr. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure, diluted with water and extracted with ether, the extract washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried ($MgSO_4$). The product obtained after removal of solvent was fractionally crystallised from methanol to yield colourless needles of 2-phenylcoumaran-3-one (0.3 g), m.p. 219° and 2-phenylcoumarone (0.1 g), m.p. 124°, mixed m.p. 123° (lit.⁴ m.p. 120°–21°).

2-p-Tolyl-3-carbomethoxyaminocoumarone: The acid chloride prepared from 2-p-tolylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid⁵ (1 g) in the usual manner was dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml) at 0° and treated with a solution of sodium azide (0.5 g) in water (4.5 ml) dropwise with stirring. After 20 min the mixture was diluted with ice-cold water when the azide (0.8 g), m.p. 98°–100° (decomp.) separated. It was collected and dried in vacuum desiccator. The i.r. spectrum showed absorptions at 1690 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and 2122 cm^{-1} (azide).

The above azide (0.8 g) was refluxed with dry methanol (10 ml) for 2 hr. Removal of alcohol afforded the urethane (0.5 g) which was crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 165° (Found : C, 72.5; H, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 72.6; H, 5.4%); ν_{max} 1700 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and 3278 cm^{-1} (N–H).

2-p-Tolylcoumaran-3-one: The above urethane (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 ml) for 40 hr. Working up in the same manner as described in the preparation of (VII), 2-p-tolylcoumaran-3-one (0.3 g) was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 225°–27°, (Found : C, 80.1;

H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 5.4%), ν_{max} 1719 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

3-Phenyl-2-carbomethoxyaminocoumarone: The acid chloride of 3-phenylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid⁶ (2 g) prepared in the usual manner was dissolved in dry acetone (20 ml) at 0° and was treated with a solution of sodium azide (0.84 g) in water (4.2 ml) dropwise with stirring. After 25 min. the mixture was diluted with ice-cold water when the azide, m.p. 81° separated. It was collected and dried.

The above azide (1.5 g) was refluxed with dry methanol for one and a half hour and then the solvent was removed to yield the desired urethane (1 g) which crystallised from methanol in cream coloured plates, m.p. 150°. (Found : C, 72.1; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.9; H, 4.9%).

3-Phenylcoumaran-2-one: The foregoing urethane (0.5 g) was refluxed with glacial acetic acid (4 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 ml) for 25 hr. Removal of solvent afforded 3-phenylcoumaran-2-one (IX) (0.2 g) which was collected, washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene as colourless plates, m.p. 115° (lit.⁷ m.p. 112°–13°). (Found : C, 80.3; H, 4.8. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O_2$, C, 80.0; H, 4.8%) ν_{max} 1800 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl).

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